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ABSTRACT

Reducing the use of chemical fertilizers is one of the objectives of the Farm to Fork Strategy (F2F) of the European Commission to reduce environmental impacts of agricultural production. To assess potential trade-offs of reduced mineral nitrogen (N) fertilization on multiple ecosystem services of soils we set up a modelling framework that allows to quantify effects on yields, soil organic carbon (SOC) storage, nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions and nitrate (NO₃) losses. We applied the SOMMIT index tool that was developed within the EJP SOIL project SOMMIT for trade-off analysis (Calone et al. 2024). This allows a quantitative assessment of the trade-offs among yields, SOC, N₂O and NO₃, presenting a comprehensive evaluation of reduced N fertilization. We calculated a SOMMIT index for each NUTS2 region in Europe and for each of the six most important crops (wheat, maize, barley, rapeseed, sugar beet, potato).

Mean SOMMIT index values differed only slightly between the different crop types, but showed high spatial variability for all crops. We identified regions with very low SOMMIT index values, suggesting that high trade-offs for yields and SOC storage occur and/or that reductions in N losses were low. In other cases, SOMMIT index values were high demonstrating that low trade-offs for yields and SOC storage and/or significant reductions in N losses are expected if mineral N fertilization would be reduced by 20 %. This variability in SOMMIT index values that we found emphasizes the unequal distribution of risks associated with reduced N fertilization for both crop yield and SOC storage and underlines the importance of region-specific approaches.

We conclude that a general implementation of reduced mineral N fertilization bears risks for crop production and SOC storage. Tools including multiple ecosystem services of soils as the SOMMIT index in combination with European-scale modelling can help identify regions with strong trade-offs as well as regions, where efforts to reduce negative impacts of high N loads could be prioritized. Such a stepped approach could help gain experience and produce valuable results for adaptive management policies as these are expanded to more vulnerable regions.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
Σ_i	SOMMIT index
T-Ocs	Trade-off components
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
RF	Random Forest
HC	Hierarchical clustering

1. Introduction

To ensure global food security, agriculture plays a very essential role, but it simultaneously poses significant environmental challenges such as soil degradation, greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity loss, and ammonia volatilization (Ladha et al., 2020). During the last decades, the use of synthetic fertilizers, especially nitrogen (N)-based fertilizers has considerably increased agricultural productivity and crop yield, which resulted in meeting the demands of a growing global population (Panhwar et al., 2019). The maximum use of N-based fertilizers also led to a wide range of environmental problems (nitrate (NO₃) leaching, contamination of ground water in the aquifers, nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions and ammonia volatilization (Tyagi et al., 2022)). All these environmental influences have urged concerns about the long-term feasibility of intensive farming systems and the sustainability of recent agricultural practices. There has been a global push towards more sustainable agricultural practices in response to overcome these environmental issues (Ahsan et al., 2021). In this regard the European Union took one of the most ambitious initiatives and launched the Farm to Fork Strategy (F2F) in 2020, which is considered one of the most essential components of the European Green Deal. The aim of the F2F is to develop a healthy and environmentally friendly food system (Mowlds, 2022). Among its several objectives, the strategy also emphasizes the need to decrease the use of different chemical fertilizers and pesticides by 50% by 2050, to mitigate environmental effects linked with intensive farming, while the health of agricultural ecosystems could additionally be enhanced by promoting biodiversity (Shah and Wu, 2019).

However, diminishing the use of N-based commercial fertilizers presents significant challenges in terms of sustaining the overall agricultural productivity and crop yield (Yadav et al., 2017). Nitrogen is considered one of the most important macro nutrients required for plant growth and development. Its availability significantly influences crop performance and productivity (Toor et al., 2021). Therefore, abrupt reductions in N fertilization rates could lead to lower yields, which could adversely affect farmers' incomes and food security which creates a complex trade-off between agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability, a challenge that lies at the core of the F2F (Antle and Valdivia, 2021).

In recent years, the awareness and importance of including potential trade-offs has increased (Lugato et al., 2018; Guenet et al 2021). Trade-off analysis has been used under a wide variability of methods i.e., optimization, econometrics, simulations of qualitative and narrative based approaches. These approaches have sometimes been used in a spatially explicit way with the help of geographic information systems (Guenet et al, 2021). In this context fuzzy logic has become an invaluable tool to study agricultural systems, which are characterized by interdependencies and uncertainties (dos Reis et al., 2023), because of its flexibility in taking into account end-user viewpoints regarding the inherent trade-offs. Target metrics are represented as continuous variables in fuzzy logic as opposed to binary values in Boolean logic. Because of this property, it may capture ambiguity, imprecision, and uncertainty about the system, which makes it a useful tool in situations when binary distinctions that are too sharp are insufficient (Zrobek et al., 2020). This methodology is especially compatible for estimating trade-offs between numerous input variables by using natural linguistics variables like "good" and "bad." In order to reflect subtle nuances, these qualitative variables are transformed into quantitative variables and are aggregated (Phillis and Andriantiatsaholiniaina, 2001). Fuzzy logic also makes it easy to include or exclude particular aspects, which helps to customize the evaluation system to fit a variety of goals and scenarios. Applications of fuzzy logic in the creation of composite indices for the evaluation of agricultural systems has proven to be versatile. This procedure has been used, for example, to assess the impact of environmental and management factors on the risk of glyphosate resistance (Ferraro and Ghera, 2013) and construct indices for agricultural sustainability across farming systems (Carozzi et al., 2013; Sami, 2013; Dos Reis et al., 2023).

To enumerate and measure the effects of a reduced N fertilizer use, a robust analytical tool is required to navigate the trade-off efficiently (Kanter et al., 2018; Antle and Valdivia, 2021). The SOMMIT index (Sustainable Organic Matter Management Index for Trade-offs) tool was developed as part of the EJP SOIL project SOMMIT to perform trade-off analysis (Calone et al., 2024). It was used to identify different soil management strategies that minimize greenhouse gases emissions (GHG) and preserve productivity (Maenhout et al., 2024). It also offers a comprehensive framework to estimate trade-offs between environmental and agricultural outcomes (Calone et al., 2024; Meanhout et al., 2024).

The SOMMIT index has been designed to integrate different agronomic (crop rotation, water use efficiency, irrigation and nutrient management, soil fertility, crop yield) and socio-economic factors (policy and regulatory environment, food security, labor availability, cost, farm income and profitability) which gives a complete view of the impacts of agricultural practices (Maenhout et al., 2024; Mello et al., 2024; Calone et al., 2024). Policymakers and researchers could easily identify the different strategies that balance productivity with environmental sustainability and also understand the results of reducing N-based fertilizers (Koskey et al., 2021). The SOMMIT index is based on different principles (sustainability, resilience, productivity and efficiency, environmental protection, economic viability, adaptive management and equity and inclusiveness) that vary frequently and their conflicting goals must be carefully considered for sustainable land management (Maenhout et al., 2024; Prudhomme et al., 2022; Simoncini et al., 2019). The goals of improving and maintaining soil fertility, diminishing environmental pollution, increasing crop yield, protecting biodiversity and diminishing different types of environmental pollution should be carefully considered when it comes to the use of N-based fertilizers (Pahalvi et al., 2021). The SOMMIT index also makes it possible to assess how alterations in N inputs influence these goals, enabling a more thorough consideration of trade-offs (Boylan et al., 2020).

Diminishing the use of N fertilizers may decrease greenhouse gas emissions but if inappropriately applied, may also decrease crop yield and soil fertility because abrupt changes in N fertilization could lead to a severe loss of crop yield due to an inadequate amount of N availability. So, the SOMMIT index tool provides information on how to mitigate these trade-off and aids in quantifying them without loss of yield and soil fertility (Calone et al., 2024; Vlek et al., 2017).

In the present study we applied the SOMMIT index for countries of the European Union to investigate the effect of a 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilization on four important indicators SOC stocks, N₂O emissions, NO₃ leaching and crop yields with a focus on six important arable crops (wheat, maize, barley, rapeseed, sugar beet, potato).

Our aim was to understand the relationships between the four indicators and to identify for which crop and in which regions/or under which pedoclimatic conditions productivity could be maintained while sustainability is increased. This study aims to improve our understanding

of how trade-offs may be avoided in practice, giving insights that are essential for the effective implementation of the F2F strategy.

2. Methodology to perform trade-off analysis

The methodology we apply was described in detail by Calone et al. (2024). In their study they apply the tool for different management practices for regions located in Italy. Here, we applied the SOMMIT index to a single management change of 20 % less mineral N fertilization and the entire European Union plus Switzerland and the UK. As spatial units we used all NUTS2 regions in which the six crops were grown or for which we received data from project partners (1059 out of 2400 NUTS2 regions). The trade-off components (T-Ocs) for the fuzzy logic model consisted of changes in yields, SOC stocks, N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching (see below).. We first created a standardized dataset by using the NUTS2 shape file in R and omitted all the cells with no values, as the original data came from different sources and had different spatial resolutions such as 10x10 km (SOC), NUTS2 (N₂O and NO₃), and national-scale (yields).

For yields, both positive and negative results could be expected by reducing N fertilizer rates and the same is true for SOC. SOC stocks are affected by changes in yields through amounts of harvest residues which deliver carbon to the soil. In contrast, N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching will likely decrease.

Figure 1. Methodological steps followed in this study

Figure 1 shows the main steps of the methodology which was followed in our study. The input data were composed of pedoclimatic conditions (precipitation, evapotranspiration, temperature and clay content) and agronomic data (organic matter inputs, crop residues, mineral nitrogen fertilization rates). The input data was analyzed by a random forest model (**see 2.3 section**) and hierarchical clustering (**see 2.4 section**). Random forest models provide predictive insights by analyzing the relationships between input variables, pedoclimatic and agronomic variables-, aiding in the understanding of how different factors contribute to improving soil ecosystem services. Hierarchical clustering helps group similar data points, facilitating the identification of distinct clusters representing different combinations of agricultural and environmental characteristics. In our study a data point refers to a NUTS2 region and thus represents a political, statistical and economic spatial unit in Europe.

2.1 Estimation of trade-off components

2.1.1 Crop yield

To estimate the response of yields to a 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilization, an approach was used based on previously published equations and data sets (Madenoglu et al. 2024). Briefly, the method is based on equations published in two meta-analysis of long-term experiments by Hijbeek et al. (2007) and van Grinsven et al. (2022), yield data from FAOSTAT (2023) and country-specific N fertilization rates provided by EJP SOIL members. Using this information changes in yields assuming a 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilization rates for the six most important arable crops grown in Europe were calculated at the national scale. This analysis included additional countries such as Turkey and Switzerland, however, they could not be included in the trade-off analysis, because the other T-Ocs could not be provided.

2.1.2 Soil organic carbon

Changes in SOC stocks of topsoils (0-30 cm) were estimated at the European-scale with the SOC model RothC applying the setup designed within the EJP SOIL project CarboSeq (Pape 2024). The amount of SOC is a balance of C input from plants and organic fertilization and C output due to mineralization. A reduction in N fertilization can lead to lower C inputs which decrease SOC stocks.

Based on the yield reductions from Madenoglu et al. (2024), we estimated the corresponding reduction in C inputs and its impact on SOC after 30 years. A literature review showed a wide

range of root biomass changes in response to N fertilization reduction, from loss to gain Bolinder & Kätterer (2024). For aboveground harvest residues, the literature generally shows straw biomass decreasing linearly with yield and the same when this is due to N fertilization. Thus, the response of root and straw biomass to N reduction is either not consistent or not apparent and, therefore, we decided to estimate the difference in C input with two common allometric functions (Bolinder et al., 2007; Franko 2011), assuming that a reduction of 20% N does not additionally change the allocation. Hence, harvest residues and roots decrease with yield.

2.1.3 Nitrous oxide emissions and nitrate leaching

Responses of nitrous oxide emissions and nitrate leaching to reductions in N fertilization were estimated using the N flow model MITERRA-Europe following the method of Velthof et al., (2009, 2014). For N₂O emissions the default IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) method was used and emission factors were derived from other models i.e., GAINS (Greenhouse Gas and Air Pollution Interactions and Synergies) and RAINS (Regional Air Pollution Information and Simulation) which were applied at the NUTS2 level without any specific regional adjustments (Lesschen et al in 2025). Nitrate leaching was estimated through different methods including runoff from agricultural soils, leaching from stored manures and from soil layers below the rooting depths (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Major steps to quantify N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching by MITERRA-Europe.

2.2 Fuzzy logic

Fuzzy logic is a way to model logical reasoning where the truth of a statement is not a binary true or false like it is with classical logic but rather it's a degree of truth that ranges from 0 which is absolutely false to 1 which is absolutely true (Mukaidono, 2001). Fuzzy logic allows us to design a fuzzy inference system which is a function that uses human interpretable rules rather than abstract mathematics, where a reference and measurements are fed in and then using a set of rules based on fuzzy logic some activating signal is produced.

Developing a fuzzy inference system doesn't require a model so it works well for complex systems whose underlying mechanisms are not fully known as long as you have some experience and intuition about the system then the rules can be developed and implemented to many different scenarios.

- Fuzzy logic is an approach that allows to assess the effect of a change on different variables simultaneously. In our study we quantify how reduced fertilization affects four different ecosystem services of soils: provisioning of food, soil C storage, regulation of greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient cycling (i.e., yield, SOC, N₂O, NO₃).
- Because the different variables have different units, they first need to be translated into linguistic variables in order to become comparable. By quantifying linguistic variables and aggregating diverse data sources, the evaluation of trade-offs between competing objectives (yield vs N-losses) is enabled. The SOMMIT index which is also known as a sustainability index, calculated by aggregating the membership function values for each T-Oc, where these membership values were ranked from 0 to 1. A \sum_i value close to 1 indicates good results of strong environmental and agricultural performance while a value closer to 0 shows bad results.

2.2.2 Fuzzy logic aggregation

In our study we used the fuzzy logic algorithm implemented in the *sets* R package, for four T-Ocs aggregated through fuzzy logic algorithm (Meyer and Hornik, 2023). We designed our fuzzy inference system with one output, the \sum_i and four inputs (T-Ocs). Both the input and the output have been scaled between 0 and 1. The weighting method was designed and the T-Ocs were aggregated into the \sum_i using fuzzy logic applied to the input information. The fuzzy

logic aggregation consisted of three varying steps i.e., fuzzification, minimum inference engine and defuzzification (**see 2.2.2 section**).

Using the membership functions, the first stage in our study was to convert the numerical inputs into fuzzy membership values. The degree to which an input belongs to each fuzzy set is described by these functions, which are specified throughout the space of the input variables. To map the T-Oc values, three fuzzy sets (low, medium, and high) have been defined. A membership function has been assigned to each fuzzy set; the 'low' and 'high' sets have sigmoidal functions, while the 'medium' set has a Gaussian function (Figure 3a and 3b). To improve the discrimination of the trade-off evaluation across case scenarios, five membership functions (very low, low, medium, high, and very high) have been assigned to the Σi (Figure 3c).

Figure 3a: Membership function values for SOC, N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching.

Figure 3b: Membership function values for crop yield.

Figure 3c: Fuzzified values obtained by the fuzzification process for T-Ocs.

The relationship between the four T-Ocs and the $\sum i$ was established via if-then rules, which governed the system's logic. With the help of 'and' logical operators, these rules covered every possible combination of the input sets, resulting in 81 rules in all.

For example, a rule might say, "The Σ_i is low if Δ SOC is 'high,' Δ N₂O is 'high,' Δ NO₃ is 'high,' and Δ yield is 'high'" (see, for example, Figure 4). The fuzzy sets related to the inputs (e.g., Δ SOC is 'high' and Δ N₂O is 'high' and Δ NO₃ is 'high' and Δ yield is 'low') combine to form the antecedent of the if-then rules, while the fuzzy sets related to the output (e.g., Σ_i is 'low') make up the consequent. For every rule, the consequent has been determined by giving each fuzzy set that corresponds to the inputs a typical numerical value, such as low = 0.15, medium = 0.5, and high = 0.85. Equation (1) has been utilized to compute a weighted average (μ) of the four T-Ocs based on these values.

To calculate the weighted average of the four T-Ocs the above three values i.e. 0.15, 0.5 and 0.85 were used in equation (1)

$$\mu = \frac{((1-SOCm)*SOCw)+((1-N2Om)*N2Ow)+((1-NO3m)*NO3w)+(Ym*Yw)}{SOCw+N2Ow+NO3w+Yw} \dots \text{Equation 1}$$

"Where; m is a representative numerical value of the fuzzy set which is attributed to each T-Oc in a specific rule while the subscript alphabet of w shows its relative weight in the above equation (Patyra and Mlynek, 1996)."

The procedure was first iterated with equal weights assigned to each T-Oc. After that, differentiable weights have been applied to derive substitute rule sets. Given the rule, the total we have 81 rules. Below we show the equations of three examples that are presented in (Fig. 4). Rule #01 shows that if Δ SOC is high, Δ N₂O is medium, Δ NO₃ is low and Δ yield is medium the Σ_i will be medium. The second rule is if the Δ SOC is medium, Δ N₂O is low, Δ NO₃ is medium and Δ yield is high so the Σ_i will be medium and the third rule is if the Δ SOC is medium, Δ N₂O is high, Δ NO₃ is high and Δ yield is medium so the Σ_i will be high. In the examples shown a balanced weight distribution is assumed (i.e. with a weight of 25 for each T-Oc). The weighted average (μ) can then be calculated using the following formulas:

$$\mu = \frac{(1-0.85)*25+((1-0.5)*25)+((1-0.15)*25)+(0.5*25)}{100} \dots \text{Equation for Rule \# 01}$$

Following that, the consequence (i.e., Σ_i) was calculated as shown below:

$\mu \leq 0.2$ $\sum i$ is very low
$0.2 < \mu \leq 0.4$ $\sum i$ is Low
$0.4 < \mu \leq 0.6$ $\sum i$ is medium
$0.6 < \mu \leq 0.8$ $\sum i$ is high
$\mu > 0.8$ $\sum i$ is very high

Thresholds for determining the fuzzy set to assign to the consequent ($\sum i$) based on the weighted average (μ) of the antecedents (trade-off components).

The process of fuzzification involved projecting the intersection of the input value from the x-axis and the membership functions to the y-axis, which reflected the computation of each input variable's membership values (T-Oc) to its associated fuzzy set (Figure 3a and 3b).

The output variable ($\sum i$)'s membership value has been ascertained through the utilization of the Mamdani minimum inference approach. By selecting the lowest value from each of the antecedent fuzzy sets and using that value to trim the output fuzzy set specified in the consequent rule, the approach uses the "min" operator to derive the fuzzy output set (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Minimum inference engine: application of the and operator to assess the rule strength based on the minimum membership values of antecedents (condition based on input variables).

The centroid approach was used for the defuzzification phase, which involves obtaining an exact measure from the total membership data (Figure 5). The center of gravity inside the aggregated fuzzy set output area is determined by this procedure, yielding a single precise value, the $\sum i$ that ranges from 0 (poor) to 1 (good).

Figure 5. For each rule a defuzzified value is obtained by the defuzzification process for the four T-Ocs.

We used the R scripts available for T-Oc aggregation and $\sum i$ computation published by (Calone et al. (2023)). To facilitate interpretation, the $\sum i$ values have been categorized using Jenks natural breaks categorization (BAMMtools R package, Rabosky et al., 2014; Calone et al., 2024). They chose this classification method over alternatives like equal intervals or quantiles because it was effective in maximizing between-group variance and optimizing within-group variance, which aligned with their goal of revealing nuanced data structures while maintaining results interpretability, despite its sensitivity to outliers and inherent subjectivity in the determination of the categories' numerosity.

2.3 Random Forest model

2.3.1 Variable importance random forest model for trade-off analysis

For regression analysis and classification, Random Forest (RF) modelling was introduced by Breiman in 2001. Random forest is an analog to a collaborative decision-making team. It creates an overall model that is more reliable and accurate by combining the predictions of nu-

merous "trees," or separate models. It is capable of handling data sets with categorical variables for classification and continuous variables for regression. In RF models the algorithm's key steps are choosing a subset of variables at random to identify the candidates for splitting at each node and drawing bootstrap samples at random. The prediction performance that is obtained from the ensemble of trees is enhanced by these random components since they decorrelate the trees.

We applied a RF model to evaluate whether environmental conditions and agronomic traits under consideration are relevant in explaining each T-Oc's (change in yield, SOC stock, N₂O emission or NO₃ leaching) variability by using the *randomForest R package* (Liaw and Wiener, 2002 and Calone et al., 2024). To make sure the results were reliable, we divided the subsample into three equally-sized folds using k-fold cross-validation (four for training and one for testing). Through trial and error, the number of trees (ntree) was optimized to 500, and the square root of the total number of predictors (mtry) was used to determine the number of predictors at each split at each tree node (Hastie et al., 2009). The root mean squared error (RMSE) was used to assess the predictive accuracy of the RF models. Despite its bias towards variables with more categories, mean decrease of impurity (MDI), rather than mean decrease in accuracy, has been chosen as a metric to assess the significance of predictors (Scornet 2023). This is mainly because of its improved processing efficiency and robustness against noise. When a decision tree is used for partitioning, MDI uses the impurity reduction at the nodes to quantify the importance of the variables. In order to facilitate comparisons between the four T-Ocs, the derived MDI values were scaled between 0 and 1.

2.4 Hierarchical clustering for trade-off analysis

We performed a hierarchical clustering analysis for the values of the four T-Ocs. Hierarchical clustering helps group similar data points, facilitating the identification of distinct clusters representing different combinations of agricultural and environmental characteristics by using the *FactoMinerR R package* (Calone et al., 2024; Le et al., 2008).

3. Results

3.1.1 Results of fuzzy logic

We calculated a Σ_i for each crop and NUTS2 region separately. The Σ_i combines the response of each T-Oc to a 20% reduction in mineral N fertilization and ranges between 0 and 1. High Σ_i values (i.e. values close to 1) mean that negative effects on yields and/or SOC storage were small and/or N losses were strongly reduced. In contrast, low values indicate strong trade-offs for yields and/or SOC storage or low reductions in N losses. The effect of a reduction in mineral N fertilization on the Σ_i varied between countries and crops (Figures 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16) due to large variation in the response of the T-Ocs (i.e. variation in yield loss, change in N₂O emissions, change in NO₃ leaching and SOC loss). There are regions with high Σ_i due to high reductions in NO₃ leaching, N₂O emissions and minor SOC losses while there are also some regions where yields decline but are associated with low reductions in NO₃ leaching and N₂O emissions and high SOC losses. In the following sections we discuss the results of each crop separately.

Generally, barley yields were negatively affected by the reduction in N fertilization as were all other crops. Yet, the Σ_i was high in the majority of countries and NUTS2 regions (Fig. 6) which could mainly be explained by a high reduction in N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching (Figs. 7b, 7c) while SOC losses were generally small (Fig. 7a). Very low Σ_i were found in 7 out of 27 countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Romania, Slovenia and Spain). This means that a 20% reduction in N fertilization led to either a strong yield reduction, a strong SOC reduction, a very low reduction in N₂O emissions or NO₃ leaching or a combination of these. In the case of barley, low Σ_i could mainly be explained by strong reductions in yields (Fig. 7d), while reductions in N₂O emissions, NO₃ leaching and SOC were rather small for Portugal and Poland countries.

Figure 6. SOMMIT index for barley. Results are shown for each NUTS2 region and are aggregated by country.

Figure 7. Average values of T-Ocs for barley for different countries. Blue dashed lines represent the overall mean across all crops and countries of each T-Oc, while the red dashed lines signify the overall mean for each crop.

In the case of maize, the Σ_i was high in the majority of countries (Fig. 8). This could mainly be explained by a high reduction in N_2O emissions and NO_3 leaching (Figs. 9b, 9c) while SOC losses were generally small (Fig. 9a). In Slovenia and the Netherlands a few regions have very high Σ_i , likely due to higher reduction in N_2O emissions and NO_3 leaching. Very low Σ_i were found in only a few countries (Czechia, Denmark, Portugal, Spain and Slovakia) and could mainly be explained by strong reductions in yields (Fig. 9d) low reductions in N_2O emissions and NO_3 leaching. Losses in SOC were rather small for these countries.

Figure 8. SOMMIT index for maize. Results are shown for each NUTS2 region and are aggregated by country.

Figure 9. Average mean values of T-Ocs of maize for different countries. Blue dashed line represents the overall mean across all crops and countries of each T-Oc, while the red dashed line signifies the overall mean for each crop.

For potato very high and high Σ_i were found in the majority of countries (Fig. 10). This could mainly be explained by a high reduction in N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching (Figs.11) while SOC losses were generally small (Fig. 11a). Spain, Malta, Finland and Belarus have very high Σ_i , while Finland and Spain have high and medium (both) Σ_i classes due to regional variations (e.g. climate variability, soil quality, water availability, agronomic practices, topographical factors) of NUTS2 regions in the cultivation of potato. Very low Σ_i were found in only a few countries (i.e., Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Slovakia, Netherlands and

Czechia) and could mainly be explained by strong reductions in yields (Fig. 11d). However, in some of these countries Σi were low in all NUTS2 regions.

Figure 10. SOMMIT index potato. Results are shown for each NUTS2 region and are aggregated by country.

Figure 11. Average mean values of T-Ocs of potato for different countries. Blue dashed lines represent the overall mean across all crops and countries of each T-Oc, while the red dashed lines signify the overall mean for each crop.

In the case of rapeseed Σ_i was high in the majority of countries (Fig. 12), which could mainly be explained by a high reduction in N_2O emissions and NO_3 leaching (Figs. 13b, 13c) while SOC losses were generally small (Fig. 13a). Very low Σ_i were found in Denmark, Estonia and Bulgaria countries and could mainly be explained by strong reductions in yields (Fig. 13d), low reductions in N_2O emissions and NO_3 leaching. Losses in SOC were rather small for these countries.

Figure 12. SOMMIT index for rapeseed. Results are shown for each NUTS2 region and are aggregated by country.

Figure 13. Average mean values of T-Ocs of rapeseed for different countries. Blue dashed lines represent the overall mean across all crops and countries of each T-Oc, while the red dashed lines signify the overall mean for each crop.

For sugarbeet the Σ_i was very high and high in the majority of countries (Fig. 14). This could mainly be explained by a high reduction in N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching (Figs. 15) while SOC losses were generally small (Fig. 15a). Very low Σ_i was found only in France and could mainly be explained by strong reductions in yields (Fig. 15d), low reductions in N₂O (Fig. 15b) emissions and NO₃ leaching (Fig. 15c). Losses in SOC were rather small for these countries.

Figure 14. SOMMIT index for sugar beet. Results are shown for each NUTS2 region and are aggregated by country.

Figure 15. Average mean values of T-Ocs of sugar beet for different countries. Blue dashed lines represent the overall mean across all crops and countries of each T-Oc, while the red dashed lines signify the overall mean for each crop.

In Belarus and Finland, the Σ_i was very high for wheat (Fig. 16). This could mainly be explained by a high reduction in N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching (Figs. 17) while SOC losses were generally small (Fig.17a). Very low Σ_i were found in about a third of the countries and could mainly be explained by strong reductions in yields (Fig. 17d) low reductions in N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching. Losses in SOC were rather small for these countries.

Figure 16. SOMMIT index for wheat. Results are shown for each NUTS2 region and are aggregated by country.

Figure 17. Average mean values of T-Ocs of wheat for different countries. Blue dashed lines represent the overall mean across all crops and countries of each T-Oc, while the red dashed lines signify the overall mean for each crop.

A summary of the SOMMIT index values of all crops is presented in Fig. 18.

Figure 18: SOMMIT index for six important arable crops presented for each NUTS2 region. Target regions for a reduction in mineral N fertilization were identified based on a very high index (e.g. parts of Spain in the case of potato or parts of the Netherlands in the case of maize). Regions with high risks for yield reductions/and or high SOC losses or regions where N losses remain high despite reduced fertilization have a low index (e.g. large parts of Italy and Greece for barley).

3.1.2. Random forest model analysis

The RF model analysis depicts the relative importance of the various agronomic and pedoclimatic factors contributing to the various trade-offs among the T-Ocs (Fig. 19). Below, we discuss the most influential factors modulating each T-Oc based on the MDI scores. In the case of SOC loss, crop residues appear to be the most important factor followed by crop type and evapotranspiration. The value for N inputs indicates moderate importance for SOC loss while the lowest MDI was recorded for clay suggesting this variable contributes little to variability in SOC loss. Changes in reductions of N₂O emissions are significantly influenced by fertilizer inputs (both mineral N and organic matter (OM)), emphasizing their importance in controlling N₂O emissions. Clay content and temperature have moderate effects on the change in N₂O emissions. The lowest MDI value was recorded for precipitation showing this factor is least important for changes in N₂O emissions. In the case of changes in NO₃ leaching, the crop type displayed the highest importance and was the most important contributing factor while all

other variables were of low importance. For yield losses, the crop type also showed the highest importance followed by the amount of crop residues and evapotranspiration whereas the lowest MDI value was recorded for precipitation.

Figure 19. Random forest model analysis to assess variables that are most important for each T-Oc. For all variables the mean decrease in impurity is shown on a scale from 0 to 1. Values near 0 show low importance while values near 1 display a strong effect for each T-Oc.

3.2.1 Results of hierarchical clustering

Four clusters emerged from the hierarchical clustering showing different patterns from the global averages for each T-Oc (Fig. 20). Cluster 01 is characterized by slightly lower SOC losses of 0.20 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ compared to the global average at 0.190 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, representing higher SOC depletion into the soil, while the change in reduction of N₂O emissions was very close to the global average (-0.34 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ vs. -0.339 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). This cluster also exhibits significantly lower NO₃ leaching -4.14 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, which is lower than the global average -3.77 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, while at the same time, yield losses of 8.5 % are considerably lower, than the global average of 10.6 %. Cluster 02 shows a lower SOC loss of 0.10 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ compared to the global mean and lower N₂O emissions reduction of -0.24 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ below the global average. The reduction in NO₃ leaching is -3.0030 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, which is slightly

lower than the global average and indicates moderate improvement in nitrogen leaching reduction. Crop yield loss of 9.03% is still lower than the global average but higher than Cluster 01, indicating relatively low to moderate changes in productivity. Cluster 3 presents, therefore, a SOC loss that is only slightly below the global average of $0.15 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, which corresponds to comparatively moderate depletion, while N_2O emissions reduction is significantly lower $-0.65 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ than the global average, indicating more environmental friendly practices. The reduction in NO_3 leaching is far above the global average $-6.30 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, pointing towards highly effective N management, whereas a yield loss of 12.32%, is just slightly above the global average, showing moderate changes in agricultural productivity. Cluster 04 shows the highest SOC loss of $0.28 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, which may indicate more intensive soil management, while reductions in N_2O emissions of $-0.23 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ are moderate compared to the global average. The reduction in NO_3 leaching $-2.70 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ is lower than the global average, indicating relatively moderate effects of N management, while average yield losses (12.7%) are slightly higher than the global average mean value of 10.6%.

Hierarchical Clustering

Figure 20. Violin box plots indicating the data distribution within four clusters for the T-Ocs. Red dashed lines show the overall-mean of each T-Oc while the thick line inside the violin box displays the median. The width of the violin box plots shows the frequency whereas the outlines of the box plots show the upper and lower quantiles.

3.2.1.1 Description of clusters with categorical variables

In the next section the clusters are described in more detail by identifying which crop types or regions were most frequently found in the respective cluster. In general, for each crop and region combination, a p-value and v-test (a measure of effect size) are provided that show how strongly these modulo variables relate to each cluster. A positive v-test value indicates that these categories are more frequently presented compared to the global average frequency while a negative value suggests the categories are underrepresented. Classification-to-model ratios (Cla/Mod) and model-to-classification ratios (Mod/Cla), both display how perfect the model is aligned with a classification.

Values of cluster 01, shows the highest v.test values for wheat and barley in comparison with the global average frequency and also showed the highest statistical significance (P.value=<0.000), while DK01, one of the NUTS2 regions in Denmark, also showed the highest frequency for these crops (Table 1). In contrast, sugar beet and potato were less frequently found in this cluster, which is indicated by negative v.test values.

Table 1. Description of cluster 01 by categorical variables.

Cluster 01					
Factors	Cla/Mod	Mod/Cla	Global mean	p.value	v.test
Crop=Barley	30.65	26.64	18.79	0.00	3.32
Crop=Wheat	30.35	26.64	18.98	0.00	3.23
NUTS2=DK01	83.33	2.18	0.57	0.00	3.04
Crop=Sugarbeet	9.86	6.11	13.41	0.00	-3.90
Crop=Potato	11.56	10.04	18.79	0.00	-4.01

Cluster 02 is dominated by maize and potato (Table 2). In contrast, sugar beet and rapeseed are underrepresented in this cluster. The NUTS2 regions that were predominantly found, were all in France (FR) showing a geographic influence on the cluster.

Table 2. Description of cluster 02 by categorical variables.

Cluster 02					
Factors	Cla/Mod	Mod/Cla	Global mean	p.value	v.test
Crop=Potato	52.26	32.30	18.79	0.00	7.18
Crop=Maize	42.94	22.67	16.05	0.00	3.78
NUTS2=FRM0	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRL0	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRK2	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRJ2	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRJ1	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRI3	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRI2	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRG0	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRF3	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
NUTS2=FRF1	80.00	1.24	0.47	0.03	2.11
Crop=Sugarbeet	22.54	9.94	13.41	0.03	-2.22
Crop=Rapeseed	1.35	0.62	13.98	0.00	-9.81

In cluster 03 positive v.test values were found for sugar beet and rapeseed, indicating their dominance in this cluster (Table 3). These crops showed a strong regional influence as expressed by NUTS2 regions including countries like Finland (FI), Spain (ES) and Germany (DE)

while less frequently observed for wheat and barley because the mean values are less than their global mean.

Table 3. Description of cluster 03 by categorical variables.

Cluster 03					
Factors	Cla/Mod	Mod/Cla	Global mean	p.value	v.test
Crop=Sugarbeet	42.96	31.28	13.41	0.00	7.38
NUTS2=DEF0	83.33	2.56	0.57	0.00	3.27
NUTS2=DE91	83.33	2.56	0.57	0.00	3.27
NUTS2=BY02	83.33	2.56	0.57	0.00	3.27
Crop=Rapeseed	28.38	21.54	13.98	0.00	3.21
NUTS2=FI1B	80.00	2.05	0.47	0.00	2.81
NUTS2=ES21	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=DEG0	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=DEA5	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=DEA2	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=DE73	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=DE71	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=DE27	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=DE21	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=BY03	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
NUTS2=BY01	66.67	2.05	0.57	0.01	2.47
Crop=Wheat	8.96	9.23	18.98	0.00	-4.07
Crop=Barley	2.01	2.05	18.79	0.00	-7.74

Results for cluster 04 showed that rapeseed and barley were the dominant crops while potato and maize had a weaker relationship with the cluster due to negative v.test values (Table 4). Among the different countries Hungary (HU), Sweden (SE) and Poland (PL) showed moderate relationships with cluster variables due to positive values of v.test. However, Cla/Mod values were higher showing the strongest relationship and a high frequency.

Table 4. Description of cluster 04 by the categorical variables.

Cluster 04					
Factors	Cla/Mod	Mod/Cla	Global mean	p.value	v.test
Crop=Rapeseed	43.24	20.45	13.98	0.00	3.81
Crop=Barley	40.70	25.88	18.79	0.00	3.73
NUTS2=PL61	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=PL52	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=PL51	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=PL42	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=PL41	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=HU33	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=HU32	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=HU31	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=HU23	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=HU22	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=HU21	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=HU11	83.33	1.60	0.57	0.01	2.55
NUTS2=SE21	80.00	1.28	0.47	0.03	2.16
NUTS2=PL43	80.00	1.28	0.47	0.03	2.16
Crop=Potato	20.10	12.78	18.79	0.00	-3.32
Crop=Maize	17.06	9.27	16.05	0.00	-4.04

3.2.1.2 Association between the cluster variables and the quantitative variables

The strength of association between cluster variables and some quantitative variables can be expressed by using both Eta^2 and P-values (Table 5). Eta^2 is a measure of the proportion of variation in the quantitative variable accounted for by the clusters; the larger the number, the stronger the association. Among the variables, changes in N_2O emissions had the highest Eta^2 indicating the strongest relationship with the clusters, explaining about 47.6% of the variance, followed by yield loss (21.1 %), and changes in NO_3 leaching (19 %). All these variables are highly significant as shown by the very low P-values (Table 5). In general, the results showed that changes in N_2O emissions, yield losses, and NO_3 leaching were dominant features in defining clusters, whereas SOC loss contributed weakly to the clustering structure with 7% Eta^2 . However, the P-value suggests this variable still has a statistically significant influence on the clustering. The other quantitative variables i.e., OM input, clay, N input, crop residues, temperature, evapotranspiration and precipitation had a smaller influence on the cluster structure.

Table 5. Link between the cluster variables and quantitative variables (chi-square test).

Variables	Eta2	P-value
Change in N ₂ Oemissions	0.48	0.00
Yield loss	0.21	0.00
Change in NO ₃ leaching	0.19	0.00
OMinput	0.08	0.00
Clay	0.07	0.00
Ninput	0.07	0.00
SOC loss	0.07	0.00
CropResidues	0.06	0.00
Temperature	0.06	0.00
Evapotranspiration	0.05	0.00
Precipitation	0.01	0.01

3.2.1.3 Description of each cluster by quantitative variables

Similar to the description above, the clusters can also be described by quantitative variables

The results for cluster 01 showed higher OM inputs compared to the overall mean and slightly stronger reductions in NO₃ leaching with a mean of -4.15 compared to the overall mean of -3.77. This cluster experiences lower yield losses of 8.56 compared to the overall mean of 10.64.

Table 6. Description of cluster 01 by quantitative variables.

Cluster 01						
Variables	Mean in category	Overall mean	sd in category	Overall sd	p.value	v.test
Change in OMinput	27.45	23.60	35.02	30.26	0.03	2.17
Change in NO ₃ leaching	-4.15	-3.77	3.49	3.02	0.03	-2.14
Yield loss	8.56	10.64	4.49	4.11	0.00	-8.63

Cluster 02 is characterized by smaller reductions in N₂O emissions, with a mean value of -0.25 versus the overall mean of -0.34, and a slightly higher clay content, with an average of 22.85 versus the overall average of 20.87. It also shows higher mean values for temperature and evapotranspiration than the overall mean (Table 7). but with lower OM input and crop residues.

Table 7. Description of cluster 02 by quantitative variables.

Cluster 02						
Variables	Mean in category	Overall mean	sd in category	Overall sd	p.value	v.test
Change in N ₂ O emissions	-0.25	-0.34	0.15	0.23	0.00	8.58
Clay	22.85	20.87	4.73	5.52	0.00	7.71
Temperature	11.24	10.41	2.90	2.76	0.00	6.45
Evapotranspiration	875.49	824.21	184.42	181.06	0.00	6.09
Change in NO ₃ leaching	-3.00	-3.77	2.04	3.02	0.00	5.47
Precipitation	888.30	864.46	228.56	218.45	0.02	2.35
CropResidues	2572.67	2688.47	857.88	847.64	0.00	-2.94
OMinput	18.16	23.60	24.96	30.26	0.00	-3.86
Ninput	55.08	64.00	35.20	34.68	0.00	-5.53
SOC loss	0.11	0.19	0.17	0.27	0.00	-6.60
Yield loss	9.04	10.64	1.23	4.11	0.00	-8.40

Cluster 03 is characterized by high N and OM inputs (Table 8). It also has higher crop residues and yield losses compared to the overall mean. Besides that, the cluster shows greater reductions in NO₃ leaching and N₂O emissions, respectively.

Table 8. Description of cluster 03 by quantitative variables.

Cluster 03						
Variables	Mean in category	Overall mean	sd in category	Overall sd	p.value	v.test
Ninput	81.94	64.00	30.42	34.68	0.00	8.00
OMinput	38.93	23.60	39.43	30.26	0.00	7.82
CropResidues	3107.62	2688.47	822.81	847.64	0.00	7.64
Yield loss	12.32	10.64	4.53	4.11	0.00	6.32
Temperature	9.78	10.41	2.33	2.76	0.00	-3.53
Clay	19.16	20.87	5.03	5.52	0.00	-4.78
Evapotranspiration	760.74	824.21	140.37	181.06	0.00	-5.42
						-
Change in NO ₃ leaching						12.9
	-6.31	-3.77	3.87	3.02	0.00	8
						-
Change in N ₂ O emissions						21.6
	-0.66	-0.34	0.17	0.23	0.00	5

Cluster 04 has higher yield losses compared to the overall mean (Table 9). Reductions in N losses were lower compared to the overall mean values. The average SOC loss was higher in this cluster possibly explained by lower OM inputs and lower clay contents.

Table 9. Description of cluster 04 by quantitative variables.

Cluster 04						
Variables	Mean in category	Overall mean	sd in category	Overall sd	p.value	v.test
Yield loss	12.77	10.64	4.00	4.11	0.00	10.89
Change in N ₂ O emissions	-0.23	-0.34	0.12	0.23	0.00	9.94
SOC loss	0.29	0.19	0.34	0.27	0.00	7.57
Change in NO ₃ leaching	-2.71	-3.77	1.58	3.02	0.00	7.44
Evapotranspiration	803.67	824.21	173.97	181.06	0.02	-2.39
Precipitation	836.62	864.46	233.69	218.45	0.01	-2.69
CropResidues	2539.20	2688.47	741.81	847.64	0.00	-3.71
OMinput	16.84	23.60	18.95	30.26	0.00	-4.71
Clay	19.62	20.87	5.92	5.52	0.00	-4.79
Temperature	9.73	10.41	2.67	2.76	0.00	-5.19

4. Discussion

A trade-off analysis was performed to capture the complex risks and benefits of a 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilization on important ecosystems services of arable soils in Europe. We applied the SOMMIT index, a newly developed tool based on fuzzy logic (Calone et al. 2024) to quantify the combined effect on yields, SOC storage, N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching. Changes in these variables were estimated using a European-scale modeling framework that we set up. Our results show that responses are spatially very heterogeneous across NUTS2 regions in Europe (Fig. 18). We identified regions with very low SOMMIT index values, suggesting high trade-offs for SOC storage and/or yields and/or low reductions in N losses. Examples are large parts of Italy and Greece for the case of barley (Fig. 6). Contrasting results were found for parts of Spain in the case of potato (Fig. 10) or parts of the Netherlands in the case of maize (Fig. 8). Here, SOMMIT index values were high demonstrating that low trade-offs for yields or SOC storage and/or significant reductions in N losses are expected if mineral N fertilization would be reduced by 20 %. This variability in SOMMIT index values that we found emphasizes the unequal distribution of risks associated with reduced N fertilization for both crop yield and SOC storage and underlines the importance of region-specific approaches. NUTS2 regions that showed high SOMMIT index values have a high potential to implement reduced N fertilization with limited risks. The regions have low vulnerability to both yield and

SOC losses, yet with high reduction potentials in N pollutants (i.e. NO_3 leaching and N_2O emissions). Focusing on these areas for initial implementation offers a strategic route toward advancing the EU's Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy (Mezzacapo, 2024). Emphasizing policy efforts in regions of low risk can more easily test the viability of reduced N fertilization with limited stakeholder resistance. Such a stepped approach also helps build experience and datasets for use in adaptive management policies as these are scaled up for application to more vulnerable regions (Bryndum-Buchholz et al., 2021).

In contrast, very low SOMMIT index values mean that a reduction in mineral N input in these areas leads to more severe yield or SOC losses and/or the desired reductions in N_2O emissions and NO_3 leaching cannot be achieved. Some of these regions may even face an increased environmental risk due to suboptimal agricultural management, soil health degradation, and inefficient N management.

Although the SOMMIT index gives a good representation of the spatial distribution of both risks and opportunities, some refinements should be considered in further studies to complete these policy recommendations based on additional factors (Fisher et al., 2019). For example, the quality of the agricultural products is usually directly influenced by N fertilization rates and needs to be taken into consideration so as not to lose market standards and consumer acceptance (Leip et al., 2014). Besides that, socio-economic aspects concerning farmers' livelihoods, such as market access and the availability of alternative technologies or practices, including precision agriculture, must be considered for the successful adoption of reduced nitrogen fertilization strategies (Boros et al., 2024). Lack of consideration might lead to resistance in farming communities and affect the wider transition toward more sustainable agricultural systems.

This study, however, underlines the importance of spatially explicit approaches in addressing the fundamental complexity of agricultural trade-offs. The SOMMIT index provides a sound framework for the identification of regions where reduced N fertilization could focus first, due to minimal risks and maximum environmental benefits. However, the implementation of reduced mineral N fertilization should be supplemented by stakeholder engagement, monitoring, and adaptive management so that the policy remains flexible and responsive to local conditions. For example, integration of the SOMMIT index with other decision-support tools and datasets could significantly enhance utility for regional and national policymaking.

Previous studies have shown that crop yield is the most sensitive component of the trade-offs studied here, although fuzzy logic models can optimize N levels to keep yield losses minimal. For example, Liu et al. (2022) showed a case where precision N fertilization technologies combined with fuzzy logic could keep yields within 5-8 % of their potential when N reduction was as high as 20-25 %. This is to prove that fuzzy logic, when combined with modern agricultural technologies, may present a promising way to balance yield and environmental sustainability - a very important need in regions like the EU, where farmers are under pressure to reduce N inputs in order to meet climate and environmental targets without compromising food production. Recently different studies have been conducted to estimate the role of SOC changes in these trade-offs. According to Lal (2020) the accumulation of SOC is a very slow process, therefore, relevant in terms of long-term soil fertility and C sequestration. Ghera (2020) also reported that the use of fuzzy logic approaches, helps farmers evaluate the gradual trade-off between immediate productivity and SOC accumulation and arrive at a decision that e.g. the incorporation of organic matter, coupled with reduced nitrogen inputs, leads to small but statistically significant increases in SOC levels over a 5-year period.

In conclusion, our results suggest that a one-size-fits-all approach to N input reduction will not be effective. Rather, strategies at the regional level that improve N efficiency, adopt precision farming technologies, and enhance soil health will be necessary to balance environmental impacts with maintaining crop yields.

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